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SUPPORTING ADOPTERS OF THE PPV300 PYROLYSIS TECHNOLOGY STRENGTHEN THEIR BUSINESS CASES

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**Supporting adopters of the PPV₃₀₀ PYROLYSIS technology
strengthen their business cases**

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COFFEE PRODUCERS' CO-OPERATIVE PYROLYSIS BASED COFFEE DRYING

SITUATION ANALYSIS

CHALLENGES faced by Vietnamese coffee producers

Globally, Vietnam holds a leading position in Robusta coffee exports. However, due to changing weather patterns, the sector is at risk. Vietnamese farmers and processors face environmental and economic challenges like water shortage, soil degradation and income losses due to unreliable drying methods and inherent coffee quality and price decline.

The state-of-the-art Pyrolysis Technology - turning coffee husks into biochar and energy for mechanical coffee drying - is a climate smart solution to enhance coffee quality and soil fertility, while mitigating CO₂ emissions.

This made-in-Vietnam technology gives the Vietnamese coffee sector access to new agro-processing technologies, to help coffee farmers making their coffee drying more cost-efficient, combat soil degradation and adapt to effects of climate change (drought, water clogging).

 Increasingly challenging climatic environment: prolonged and heavy rainfall during the harvest season followed by droughts

Severe soil degradation due to decades of intensive coffee farming and extreme climate requiring increasingly high usage of chemical fertiliser

 Large volumes of unused biomass residues (such as coffee husks) are left to decompose in open piles; resulting in GHG emissions and a loss of valuable organic matter

 Loss of income of farmers by up to 20%: due to unstable sun-drying conditions resulting in mouldy coffee cherries and compromised product quality

 Disputes with local residents and authorities raised from health and pollution concerns due to smoke emissions resulting from the inefficient coffee drying burners

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THE SOLUTION

Pyrolysis technology and in particular biochar have been highlighted as tools to fight climate change while also improving soil fertility and providing a source of heat energy

Pyrolysis and Biochar systems provide a viable solution for some of the challenges faced by Vietnamese farmers today

THE TECHNOLOGY

The Pyrolysis technology - PPV300 “Le Viet”

The PPV300 Pyrolysis technology, manufactured and implemented by the Vietnamese company Viet Hien (www.viethien.vn), is designed specially for use as a coffee drying system by the Vietnamese coffee sector. It valorizes coffee husks/biomass in a controlled manner to provide two main products:

- Heat, which can be used for efficient and quick coffee drying
- Biochar, a valuable soil enhancer (and a potential new product-line)

The Pyrolysis-Technology:

1. Input of biomass waste
2. Reactor: Thermal decomposition of organic compounds and production of burnable gases. The gases are transported to the burner
3. Burner: generates heat
4. Transfer of heat to an attached drum dryer where it is used for the drying of coffee beans
5. Output of biochar

Input Material: Coffee husks (cashew, cocoa, coconut, rice, pomace, etc.)

Biomass input: 100 kg/h

Biochar output: 30 kg/h

Capacity of the drum dryer: 4 tons

Runtime per drying cycle: 20h

Height: 6.50 m

Length: 6.70 m

Weight: 3000 kg

Produced heat: 300 kW

Gas consumption: 4 liter/cycle

Duration of a cycle: 6 days

Power consumption: 6 kWh

HEAT - for coffee drying

The heat produced by the pyrolysis machine is transferred to an attached dryer with a capacity of 4 tons, in which the coffee cherries are dried at 300°C for 20 hours to reach a moisture content of 12%. The dryer guarantees high quality production of coffee beans through homogenous drying.

BIOCHAR - pyrolysis by-product

Biochar is the solid product remaining after the pyrolysis process. It may be used as a soil enhancer and could help reduce the input of chemical fertilizers. Key properties relevant to its use as a natural soil enhancer:

- Increased soil pH
- Enhanced water holding capacity
- Reduced fertilizer needs
- Improved soil structure
- Increase yields

Coffee husks (left) & biochar (right)

The PPV300 technology provides a promising alternative to help reduce costs and bring new business opportunities to coffee farming/processing co-operatives in Vietnam

How much you have to invest...

The PPV 300 pyrolysis system is recommended for co-operatives or farms producing 500 tons of fresh cherries per year. Based on the average Vietnamese Coffee production (10 t fresh cherries/ha), this signifies the PPV 300 has a capacity to process coffee cherries from an area of 50 ha.

INVESTMENT COSTS

The PPV 300 system costs 49'000 \$.

It comprises of:

- A pyrolysis system 40'000 \$
- A drum dryer: 6'600 \$
- Other Equipment: 2'400 \$

“Active coffee drying, a reduction in processing time, improvement in the quality of dried beans and the additional benefits from biochar as a soil enhancement were the decisive points for us to invest in the PPV300 system.”

– Binh Minh Coop

OPERATION

Per year the following economic benefits could occur:

- Energy costs: – 900 \$
 - Yearly maintenance (15%): – 7300 \$
 - Coffee income, better quality: + 15'000 to 31'000 \$
 - Additional yield due to biochar: + 4400 to 23'200 \$
(based on coffee, black pepper and durian)
 - Possible fertilizer savings: + 0 to 230 \$
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- Yearly additional income: 11'200 to 46'230 \$

...and what you could earn

The strength of the pyrolysis system lies on two main pillars: quality related improvements of the coffee drying and the higher yield provided by the application of biochar.

HIGHER COFFEE QUALITY

Farmer using a PPV300 will benefit from better coffee quality, as the drying-based deductions can be minimized. The higher quality will lead to a higher and more stable coffee price and income.

HIGHER YIELD

Thanks to the refinement of coffee husk into biochar, the bio-resource is preserved and can either be used directly by the co-op to increase yields in their farms or be sold on the local market. The yield increase for pepper, durian or coffee could be between 5 to 25 %.

“Our experience with biochar as a soil enhancer shows clear benefits. The productivity of pepper is better - reduced death rate and the plants are healthier compared to fields without biochar use.” – Binh Minh Coop

With the additional income provided by the PPV 300 system, the payback period or Return on Investment (ROI) can be less than three years

Experience of early adopters

“The pyrolysis system is especially useful when the rainy season coincides with the coffee harvest season – as it allows for drying of coffee beans without them becoming mouldy.”

“As technical skilled labor is required to operate and maintain the system, installation of the PPV 300 created 2 new jobs for the community.”

**Binh Minh
Farmers' Co-op**
(PPV 300 user
since 2016)

“The use of biochar in our pepper farming has helped increase yields.”

Our current focus is to enhance the quality and range of our biochar products and build our biochar brand to be recognized widely in the Vietnam market.”

**Viet Hien
Mechanical Co.**
(PPV 300 manufacturer
& Biochar producer)

“The PPV 300 provides a great solution for enterprises (SMEs) operating in the agricultural product value chain - processing enterprises and millers.”

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